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**One Application of Wallis
Theorem**

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One Application Of Wallis Theorem¹

Theorem 1. (Wallis, 1616-1703)

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^{2n-1} x dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos^{2n-1} x dx = \frac{2.4 \dots (2n)}{1.3 \dots (2n+1)}$$

Proof. Using integration by parts, we obtain

$$I_n = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^{2n-1} x dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^{2n} x \sin x dx = -\cos x \cdot \sin 2nx \Big|_0^{\pi/2} + 2n \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^{2n-1} x (1 - \sin^2 x) dx = 2nI_{n-1} - 2nI_n$$

from where $I_n = \frac{2n}{2n+1} I_{n-1}$.

By multiplication we obtain the statement. We prove in the same way for $\cos x$.

Theorem 2. $\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin^{2n} x dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos^{2n} x dx = \frac{1.3 \dots (2n-1) \pi}{2.4 \dots (2n) \cdot 2}$

Proof. Same as the first theorem.

Theorem 3. If $f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{2k} x^{2k}$, then

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} f(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} f(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} a_0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_{2k} \frac{1.3 \dots (2k-1)}{2.4 \dots (2k)}$$

Proof. In the $f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{2k} x^{2k}$ function we substitute x by $\sin x$ and then integrate from 0 to $\pi/2$, and we use the second theorem.

Theorem 4. If $g(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_{2k+1} x^{2k+1}$, then

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} g(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} g(\cos x) dx = a_1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_{2k+1} \frac{2.4 \dots (2k)}{1.3 \dots (2k+1)}$$

Theorem 5. If $h(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k x^k$, then

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} h(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} h(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} a_0 + a_1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} a_{2k} \frac{1.3 \dots (2k-1)}{2.4 \dots (2k)} + a_{2k+1} \frac{2.4 \dots (2k)}{1.3 \dots (2k+1)} \right)$$

Application 1.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sin(\cos x) dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{1}{1^2 3^2 \dots (2k+1)^2}$$

Proof. We use that $\sin x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{x^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!}$.

Application 2.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \cos(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{4^k (k!)^2}$$

Proof. We use that $\cos x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{x^{2k}}{(2k)!}$.

Application 3.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} sh(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} sh(\cos x) dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1^2 3^2 \dots (2k+1)^2}$$

Proof. We use that $sh x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!}$.

¹Together with Mihály Bencze.

Application 4. $\int_0^{\pi/2} ch(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} ch(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^k (k!)^2}$.

Proof. We use that $ch x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k}}{(2k)!}$.

Application 5.

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$$

Proof. In the arcsin $x = x + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1.3 \dots (2k-1)x^{2k+1}}{2.4 \dots (2k)(2k+1)}$ expression we substitute x by $\sin x$, and use theorem 4. It results that $\pi^2 / 8 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2}$. Because $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 1/k^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2} + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 1/k^2$

we get $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 1/k^2 = \pi / 6$.

Application 6. $\int_0^{\pi/2} \sin x \operatorname{ctg}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \cos x \operatorname{ctg}(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{B_k}{(k!)^2}$

where B_k is the k -th Bernoulli type number (see[1]).

Proof. We use that $x \operatorname{ctg} x = 1 - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{4^k B_k}{(2k)!} x^{2k}$

Application 7.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{arctg}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{arctg}(\cos x) dx = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{2.4 \dots (2k)}{1.3 \dots (2k-1)(2k+1)^2}$$

Proof. We use that $\operatorname{arctg} x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{x^{2k+1}}{2k+1}$

Application 8.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{argth}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{argth}(\cos x) dx = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2.4 \dots (2k)}{1.3 \dots (2k-1)(2k+1)^2}$$

Proof. We use that

Application 9. $\operatorname{argth} x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2k+1}}{2k+1}$.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{argsh}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{argsh}(\cos x) dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2}$$

Proof. We use that $\operatorname{argsh} x = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{1.3 \dots (2k-1)x^{2k+1}}{2.4 \dots (2k)(2k+1)}$

Application 10.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{tg}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{tg}(\cos x) dx = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^{2k-1}(4^k - 1)B_k}{1^2 3^2 \dots (2k-1)^2 k}$$

Proof. We use that

$$\operatorname{tg} x = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^{2k}(4^k - 1)B_k}{(2k)!} x^{2k-1}$$

Application 11.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\sin x}{\sin(\sin x)} dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos x}{\sin(\cos x)} dx = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2^{2k-1} - 1)B_k}{2^{2k} (k!)^2}$$

Proof. We use that
$$\frac{x}{\sin x} = 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2^{2k-1} - 1)B_k}{(2k)!} x^{2k}$$

Application 12.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\sin x}{sh(\sin x)} dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos x}{sh(\cos x)} dx = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2^{2k-1} - 1)B_k}{2^{2k} (k!)^2}$$

Proof. We use that
$$\frac{x}{sh x} = 1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(2^{2k-1} - 1)B_k x^{2k}}{(2k)!}$$

Application 13.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \sec(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sec(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{E_k}{2^{2k+1} (k!)^2}$$

where E_k is the k -th Euler type number (see([1])).

Proof. We use that
$$\sec x = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{E_k}{(2k)!} x^{2k}$$

Application 14.

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{sech}(\sin x) dx = \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{sech}(\cos x) dx = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{E_k}{2^{2k+1} (k!)^2}$$

Proof. We use that

$$\operatorname{sech} x = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{E_k}{(2k)!} x^{2k}$$

References:

- [1] Octav Mayer: Teoria funcțiilor de o variabilă complexă, Ed. Academică, București, 1981.
- [2] Mihály Bencze, About Taylor-formula (manuscript).